

Common strategies and avant-garde approach in terrestrial laserscanning

D Blersch¹, C Held¹, M Mettenleiter¹, C Fröhlich¹ and M Ioannides²

¹ Zoller + Fröhlich GmbH, Simoniusstr. 29, 88239 Wangen, Germany

² Cyprus University of Technology, Arch. Kyprianou 31, 3036 Limassol, Cyprus

Email: d.blersch@zofre.de, marinos.ioannides@cut.ac.cy

Abstract. Over the years, terrestrial laserscanners evolved in terms of speed, accuracy and range. Key aspect of a successful project is an efficient workflow of data capturing and pre-processing. Latest novel developments in hardware and software allow to drastically reducing field and office time, affecting each stage of the workflow: Scan Location Planning, Data Capture, Filtering/Cleaning, Registration and Analysis. Moreover, automatic registration algorithms improved recently. However, a good pose estimation, user-defined or with the help of further sensors can reduce the processing complexity dramatically, especially in large projects. In addition, these sensors open up the possibility of real-time registration in the field, shifting the pre-processing stage into the field. Additional data acquisition sensors were combined with laserscanners, such as integrated HDR cameras or calibrated external infrared cameras. This allows on a first worldwide holistic approach to automatically assign an RGB together with a temperature value to each geometry pixel and to analyse the scenery with new aspects which opens up new workflows. This unique 6D data acquisition (x, y, z; intensity; texture; temperature) technology is the most efficient and currently available to be used in the area of Cultural Heritage documentation. The paper presents the novel technology and demonstrates the latest developments and their benefits especially for Cultural Heritage applications in the area of UNESCO WHL monuments such as the ASINOU Church, the ancient Amphitheatre and mosaics documentation at the archaeological park of Kourion in Cyprus.

1. Current standards of 3D terrestrial laserscanners

In the years around 1998 the terrestrial 3D laserscanner technology reached the civil market as commercial products and rapidly evolved. Initially with a rigid limited field of view the devices qualified as valuable entry to the family of professional survey technology. Generally seen, while in the first decade improvement of technical specifications and processing software took place, the beginning of the second decade showed the integration of additional sensors.

Today's high end class of static 3D terrestrial laserscanners has - with exceptions - some general characteristics. The models are based on a stand-alone concept. Power supply, data storage and the control panel have been integrated on-board in order to avoid additional packages and sensible connection cables during the operation. The panoramic horizontal field-of-view (360°) is widely adapted and the vertical field-of-view reaches up to 320°. Ranges vary from thirty to several hundreds of meters, even kilometers in some cases and scanning speed has already passed the 1 mio px/sec data rate. Certifications on eye safety (laser class 1) and ingress protection (IP class 53 and higher) have

been reached. The operability is given in many cases at temperatures below zero degrees centigrade. Some do have Wi-Fi connection which is mainly used for remote control.

2. Output data

2.1. 3D Laserscanners

The heart of a 3D laser scanner is given by the electronic distance measuring device, the mechanical deflection unit of the laser beam and the controller. The capturing process works point wise in a polar system by reading the deflection angles and the range with the laser range finder.

Figure 1. Technical principle of a laser range finder.

The individually altering reflection ratio of each coordinate has visual reading properties of different materials of the captured surfaces when applied on a grayscale. This intensity value depends mainly on the surface reflection properties, the distance to the sensor and the incident angle of the laser beam.

Figure 2. Operation principle of a 3D terrestrial laserscanner.

During operation the device gets mounted on a tripod being fixed at its base. The laser beam is sent out and deflected in a vertical plane (vertical deflection) via a rotating mirror while the system itself rotates horizontally (horizontal deflection) resulting in spherical sensing of the surroundings [3].

A panoramic laserscan typically consists of about 12 – 50 million coordinates which are saved in a file as a point cloud. The capturing result is a cloud of spatial coordinates (x, y, z) with intensity values. Both are stored inside the Z+F scan file format *.ZFS which is linked to a Z+F project file *.ZFPRJ.

2.2. Additional sensors: the High Dynamic Range (HDR) camera Z+F I-Cam

Since laser light uses a certain wavelength, the measured data results monochrome at the wavelength of the emitted laser light. By evaluating the signal level of the backscattered laser light (measured intensity) it is possible to generate gray scale reflectivity images [2].

For a long time photographic color information had been of auxiliary use for orientation purpose. The introduction of HDR technology significantly helped to establish it as a valuable additional information layer on scan data. Valuable color information enhances significantly the analysis and assessment of materials by their visual state. For instance, industrial environments use color coding in conducts for communication of fundamental properties, e.g. blue = cold / red = hot / yellow = gas. Nowadays, accurate color information is considered indispensable for surveys of cultural and architectural heritage, where the documentation value is very high [5].

Manual alignment of color information to the scan data is complex and prone to errors. Modern laser scanners record the color information of the surrounding area by additional internal or external sensors using an additional work cycle right after the 3D capturing. The camera is directed to a number of predefined positions from which the relevant surrounding areas are captured. Devices with a rigidly integrated camera allow applying a predefined calibration protocol in order to match each camera pixel to the corresponding scan pixel by known transformation parameters fully automatically and with constant accuracy. Therefore the result arrives rapidly and has a constant and reliable quality [4]. The raw color data is stored in a ZFI file (Z+F imagery) and after processing in a JPG / PNG.

Figure 3. Device with integrated camera (center) and accessorial headlight (top right).

Figure 4. HDR colored point cloud in 2D view (extract). Architectural details, e.g. the roof overhang, are documented without loss due to interferences with incorrect exposure times.

For some devices it is possible to extend the application range to dark environments up to complete darkness, using accessorial headlight with directed LED emitters. Within indoor ranges it improves significantly the color result and avoids disturbing shadows.

Figure 5. Bundle of raw imagery from the Z+F I-Cam with different exposures for HDR processing.

The integrated High Dynamic Range technology [1] allows operation under light conditions of high contrasts, which is common in laser scanning applications especially when using full panorama views.

By the use of exposure series the correct color information is being detected also in these parts which conventionally would result under- or overexposed. A bundle of images is captured for each camera position. The final panorama is generated pixel-by-pixel from the best exposure values. Therefore, photographic color mapping of point clouds is possible even in conditions of extreme contrasts.

2.3. Additional sensors: Infrared camera Z+F T-Cam

As first manufacturer Z+F introduced a calibrated thermal camera with a one-click full panorama processing solution (Z+F T-Cam) which associates a temperature value with each geometric point.

Manually merging of thermal imagery to point clouds had been quite complex because their extremely different resolutions. The lower level of detail of thermal images impacts negatively on manual assignment of homologous points between them. Hardware with higher resolution still hardly matches the integration conditions such as on energy consumption, cooling, size and weight.

Figure 6. Accessorial infrared camera Z+F T-Cam.

Figure 7. Thermal analyzing tool with and without enhanced visibility by the transparent point cloud allows (left).

The Z+F T-Cam is a calibrated compact add-on camera and is controlled and powered directly from the scanner. Within one single cycle the temperature information of the surfaces is captured in an additional step (after the geometry and RGB color). Similar to the integrated color camera I-Cam, the software applies the automated color mapping to the scan data [9]. The parallax effect induced by the offset position is negligible at architectural scale. The visual data combination of scan and infrared imagery is enhanced by toggling dynamically the transparency. The high resolution of the scan data allows the sharp and accurate definition of the geometries (e.g. edges and borders) while the thermal data shows the temperature on the surfaces with less resolution [1].

The T-Cam allows using temperature as further criteria for analysis, segmentation and classification of scanned objects. Color information may provide knowledge about the condition and contents of an architectural element. Thermography may provide time-related knowledge about heat distribution on the surfaces. Further it allows detecting, locating and identifying the presence of damages such as cracks and leaks by indirect reading of dynamic effects, e.g. temperature changes by evaporation.

The raw data of the thermal camera is stored in the format *.IR.ZFI (Z+F Infrared imagery) and after processing in *.JPG /PNG and *.IR.TIFF.

3. Common project workflow in static 3D terrestrial laserscanning

Survey projects are generally articulated in field work and office work. In comparison to conventional survey methods (direct, indirect, manual, digital etc.) where the operator classifies the geometrical elements already in the field and transcribes them with his own abstraction to a scaled deliverable, the laserscanning survey has a different character. On site, it is a panoramic capturing at a defined

resolution but without any classification of the captured geometries. The interpretation of the geometries is disconnected from the site in place and time.

3.1. Conventional workflow with targetless registration

The laserscanning survey is structured in a data capturing phase in the field, the successive assembly of the scans (registration, together with filtering and coloring) and then the data interpretation phase, both in the office.

Figure 8. Conventional workflow in terrestrial 3D laserscanning.

4. The Blue workflow: an avant-garde approach

The data assembly bears the risk of failure during the registration which is always connected to extra costs when appearing back in the office. The risk varies with the applied registration method.

Target registration methods generally have higher reliability, but are a factor of additional effort and have limitations when used without redundancies.

Figure 9. The Blue Workflow introduced by Zoller + Fröhlich in 2015.

Registration methods without targets by form (cloud-to-cloud) or by fitted planes (plane-to-plane) allow waiving the additional target setups in the field, but demand extensive hardware resources for

processing. They are sensible to fail because of missing overlaps between scans and high ratio of moving objects. Often the processing may require intervention by an operator in case of failure, at any time during the cycle which is a limitation for overnight batch processing.

Zoller + Fröhlich developed the *Blue Workflow* which is a novel approach designed strictly on user needs by shifting the data assembly phase from the office to the field. The Blue Workflow is available for use with the product Z+F IMAGER[®] 5010X and its tablet software Z+F LaserControl[®] Scout.

The solution synchronizes the incoming scan data to a tablet-PC, performs an automatic real-time registration. Further efficient auxiliary tools allow manual correction and the optimization of the registration (fine registration) to be done as background operation during idle times.

As a result, the operator leaves the site with the already registered project and may proceed in the office immediately with data interpretation. For full flexibility, the user may switch between the Blue Workflow and the conventional workflow at any time and without technical limitations.

4.1. Automatic target-less registration on site and in real-time

The risk of additional cost infliction due to registration issues is a negative factor regarding the efficiency of targetless surveys, since causing a higher demand of redundancies in the field. In other words, the dilemma is in the ratio between cutting off the extra effort of target set-ups and increasing significantly the number of scan positions not only for the required overlaps, but in order to be on the safe side during registration. The Z+F solution is based on the cloud-to-cloud registration principle, but allows flexible integration of all other methods.

4.1.1. Requirements. Shifting the critical assembly phase from the office to the field allows for the first time to take countermeasures immediately and directly on site. The operation needs to harmonize with the frequency of setting up the scan positions in order to avoid any additional time or delay.

The mandatory hardware requirements are [7]:

- An external data computation unit such as a tablet PC for off-board processing, physically and logically independent from the scanner.
- High-speed wireless data exchange between the scanner and the tablet PC.
- Wi-Fi signal at extended range.
- Additional sensors for pose estimation of the scanner, with indoor and outdoor capabilities.
- independence from battery runtime of the tablet PC.

The mandatory software requirements are [8]:

- Close to real-time processing of the registration.
- The result needs be immediately available for evaluation and eventual countermeasures.
- Efficient correction tools are needed in case of negative outcome.
- All additional basic processes must fit within the tight time window of the typical retention time in a scan position (a couple of minutes).

4.1.2. Positioning sensors for automatic registration. Z+F LaserControl[®] Scout is based on the cloud-to-cloud registration principle which is able to perform without any additional preliminary processes, such as indexing. Initial alignment of two scans is mandatory for cutting processing time since the algorithm iteratively searches by radius for matching point groups.

The initial alignment is done by the system automatically. The data derives from additional positioning sensors, such as GPS and IMU (positioning, with indoor and outdoor capability for stop-and-go scans), barometer (height) and compass (orientation). The pose estimation is sent together with the scan file from the scanner to the tablet and gives the relative position and orientation to the preceding scan [6][7].

Figure 10. The Z+F IMAGER® 5010X with integrated indoor and outdoor positioning system for stop-and-go operation. It tracks the movements while being carried and estimates the set-up position and scanner orientation. Two dual-band antennas for data transmission and remote control allow constant synchronization with the Z+F LaserControl® Scout tablet.

4.1.3. *Cloud-to-cloud registration with real-time performance.* In order to achieve the sufficient performance for real-time operations, the cloud-to-cloud registration principle is split up in two requisitions:

- A) Creation of connectivity between two scans (evaluation factors: overlap, resolution, noise)
- B) Computing of the maximum registration accuracy by iterative algorithms

The interrelations between the requisitions are:

- If condition A is positive, then the result of B is also positive and improves by processing.
- If condition A is negative, then B is obsolete. Corrective countermeasures need to be applied by the operator.

These requisitions have the properties:

- A) Rapid computation if computed in 2D. Positive result will also apply for 3D
- B) Complex 3D computation which can be done during idle times in batch mode. Negligible risk of failure, if A is positive

The result has the potential of an extremely rapid field-registration tool used as a reliable verification of the connectivity between scans and a subsequent robust optimizer tool for batch processing.

Figure 11. Next incoming scan and placement in estimated position by navigation sensors. Automatic 2D registration or manually as corrective tool with maximum moving radius resulting in a verified connectivity and alignment.

4.1.4. Correction tools. Immediate countermeasures consist either in individual parameter setting for the computation or in correction of resolution (by doing a subscan) or in adding overlaps (from an intermediate scan position).

The Z+F solution proposes intuitive and efficient manual tools at two levels of complexity [8]. The first tool is based again on 2D matching principle of the ground view, but with manual adjustment in position and orientation and further of the allowed maximum moving radius (figure 11). The more restrictive the radius, the more robust becomes the computation. Further, this is a powerful tool to avoid false positive results due to geometrical similarities of repeated structures. The second tool is a real 3D computation of two scans with an intuitive manual alignment interface. The two tools can be combined and enhanced by manual modification of the relation between scans. These tools have touch-screen optimized interfaces for tablet-PC.

4.2. Extension of the Blue Workflow

The introduction of an external tablet PC with full control of the real-time model building process keeps a vast potential for additional features.

4.2.1. Support for external scanners. Scanning with a handheld device of hidden areas, details or any filigree decorative parts of a scene, such as capitals of columns or sculptural elements, while the static scanner is capturing the overall scene is very efficient. The external scan data can be transferred to the tablet PC and registered to the project [8]. It is possible to synchronize the scan data directly to the project of the Z+F scanner and register it on-the-fly.

Figure 12. Synchronization with external sensors for integrated use. Advanced automatic synchronization allows upload from handheld scanner (e.g. DotProduct DPI-8) to Z+F IMAGER[®] 5010X, insertion to the running scan project and instant transfer to the tablet for manual registration into the current digital model.

4.2.2. Additional batch processing. The real-time automatic registration feature is optimized for operating parallel to the active capturing cycles of the scanner device. The operator alters between moving the scanner to the next position and registering the incoming scan with the previous position. Time in between operation of the scanner can be used for batch processing, such as fine registration, coloring and filtering [8][9].

5. The Blue Workflow and Inception

The instant full control over the digital model directly on site allows re-thinking the terrestrial laserscanner as an instant tool for verification, documentation and assessment. The Blue Workflow has created an ideal platform for context specific features such as in Cultural Heritage. Having the complete digital model instantly in hand is the basic practical condition for enriching the captured geometry with intelligence, while still on site.

Figure 12. Visual state of the scan project at the end of field work. Times during logistics have been used for complete batch processing, such as fine registration, filtering and HDR coloring.

The holistic approach of the Horizon 2020 project Inception for Heritage-Building Information Modeling (H-BIM) includes purposeful data collection already from capturing level. The Blue Workflow is the ideal environment for the insertion of differentiated and context-sensitive tools.

6. Field verification of the Blue Workflow

Our methodology has been tested in two different case studies on the Island of Cyprus. The first selected site was the Archaeological Site of Asinou, which is a byzantine Church and the second was a Greco-Roman time period Amphitheatre of the Kourion Archaeological Site near Limassol which is the second biggest city on the island.

Both case studies are not only remarkable sites, but also very unique for the implementation and testing of our methodology. Moreover, their exposure to environmental factors such as earthquakes, high temperatures and humidity are challenging the e-documentation of the two unique sites.

6.1. Case study: Church of Panagia Phorbiotissa of Asinou

The famous Byzantine painted church of Panagia Phorbiotissa of Asinou is situated about five kilometers south of the village of Nikitari in the pine-clad of the Troodos range of mountains, at an altitude of approximately 450m. The church is dedicated to the Virgin Mary and is considered to be one of the most important Byzantine churches in Cyprus. The main church is the only surviving part of the Phorves monastery from which the name Panagia Phorvotissa originates. The church is dated from the early 12th century AD and the murals inside range from the 12th century through the 17th century. The church is recognized as a World Heritage Monument by UNESCO, as it is home to perhaps the finest examples of Byzantine Mural paintings of the island.

The church is a rectangular vaulted, humble-looking building with arched recesses in the side walls and transverse arches supporting the vault. It is built with local volcanic irregular stones originally covered with plaster in such a way as to imitate marble revetment. The church is covered with a steep-pitched roof and flat tiles. The original piers with the transverse arches were strengthened with additions at a later date. The apse of the church was also reinforced with additions at a later date. A narthex, with two semi-circular apses and calotte and a drumless dome, and apsidal north and south ends, was added at the west end at about the end of pitched roof with flat tiles, which appear in the model of the church in the donor composition, and therefore is original. The structure was built in the

12th century by the Greeks, who also built the nearby ancient city of Asinou. The transverse arches were strengthened with additions at a later date. It appears that the church suffered great damage at the end of the 13th, or beginning of the 14th century as the result of an earthquake. The apse was then rebuilt and the apse semidome and nave were redecorated. The narthex was redecorated in 1332/3. Thus the frescoes surviving in the church of Asinou today vary in date.

Fortunately, two-thirds of the original decoration of the church of 1100's survives today. Through these murals we are able to determine that the church was probably originally constructed as a family chapel for Nicephoros Magistros (who later died here in 1115 AD). One inscription found in the south-west recess records that the church of the holy mother of God was painted through the donation and great desire of Nicephoros Magistros the Strong, when Alexios Comnenos was Emperor in the year 6614, indiction 14. This probably means that the church was constructed sometime between the year 1099 and 1105. Another inscription mentions that the founder was also called "the Strong", an appellation most probably given to him by the people for his power and severity as a judge, or taxation officer. The inscriptions mention neither a Monastery nor the appellation "Phorbiotissa".

6.2. Case study: Amphitheatre of Kourion

Kourion / Curium, an ancient Greek city on the southwestern coast of Cyprus, the surrounding Kouris River Valley being occupied from at least the Ceramic Neolithic period (4500-3800 BCE) to the present. The acropolis of Kourion, located 1.3 km southwest of Episkopi and 13 km west of Limassol, is located atop a limestone promontory approximately 43-51m in height along the shore of Episkopi Bay. The Kourion archaeological area lies within the Akrotiri Sovereign Base Area, which forms part of the British Overseas Territory of Akrotiri and Dhekelia.

Figure 13. Thermal analysis tool in Z+F LaserControl[®] Scout for on-site assessment.

In the Cypro-Archaic period (750-475 BCE) the Kingdom of Kourion was among the most influential kingdoms of Cyprus. In 672 Damasos, king of Kourion, is recorded as a tributary of Esarhaddon of Assyria as Damasu of Kuri. Between 569 and approx. 546 BCE Cyprus was under Egyptian administration. In 546 BCE Cyrus I of Persia extended Persian authority over the Kingdoms of Cyprus, including the Kingdom of Kourion. During the Ionian Revolt (499-493BC), Stasanor, king of Kourion, aligned himself with Onesilos, king of Salamis, the leader of a Cypriot alliance against the Persians. In 497 Stasanor betrayed Onesilos in battle against the Persian general Artybius, resulting in a Persian victory over the Cypriot poleis and the consolidation of Persian control of Cyprus.

Our second case study: The Kourion Amphitheater, initially constructed in the 2nd century BC, was relatively small. Renovations in the mid-1st century and at the beginning of the 2nd century

reconstructed and expanded the theatre. In the early-3rd century the theatre was renovated to accommodate gladiatorial games. The theatre was abandoned in the later-4th century. The cavea could accommodate 3,500 spectators. The stage building (scaenae frons) is preserved only in its foundations, though this would have originally obscured the view of the Mediterranean to the south. The theatre has been completely restored and is used today for open air performances. It is one of the venues for the International Festival of Ancient Greek Drama.

6.3. The results

The missions to the UNESCO WHL monument Asinou and the Kourion amphitheatre have been very valuable, due to the unique opportunity to fully use the hardware and software above. The entire interior and the exterior of the monument have been scanned in an extremely short time window: six hours. By the end of the day we had the exact 3D structure, the Infrared values and the photographic Texture of the entire monument.

The following images are illustrating the exact, amazing and unique results, which have articulated for the first time at the full assembly meeting of the Sub-Committee for Culture, Diversity and Heritage of the Council of Europe in Limassol in November 2015.

Figure 14. Ground plan of Asinou church from the point cloud.

Figure 15. Section view with HDR colors of the decorations (Asinou).

7. Conclusions

In this paper we presented a novel hardware and software infrastructure for the holistic digitalization and 3D modelling of important Cultural Heritage monuments. The system can work under unusual extreme conditions and can be used for any kind of buildings / monuments. The advantage to be able to update the holistic 3D models on site and on-time is worldwide unique and a breakthrough for the area of Cultural Heritage digital documentation.

References

- [1] Fröhlich C, Mettenleiter M, Held C, Bleresch D and Kurz S 2015 Surveying by means of both 3D Geometry with HDR Colour and Thermal Imagery *Automatisierungstechnik* **63-4** 279–85
- [2] Fröhlich C 1993 Aktive Erzeugung korrespondierender Tiefen- und Reflektivitätsbilder und ihre Nutzung zur Umgebungserfassung. *Diss. Dep. Autom. Contr. Eng. Tech. Univ. Munich* Pro Universitate
- [3] Abmayr T, Härtl F, Hirzinger G, Burschka D and Fröhlich C 2009 Calibration and registration framework for reconstruction of the Kirche Seefeld *Proc. ISPRS w.gp.* **38-5/W1**
- [4] Rüter H, Held C, Schröder R, Bhurtha R and Wessels S 2012 From Point Cloud to Textured Model. Zamani laser scanning pipeline in heritage documentation. *S. Afric. J.Geomatics* **1-1**

- [5] Leisen H, Büttner E, Obertreiber N and Reinköster M 2009 Fusion von Laserscanning und Bild-
daten zur Schadensanalyse am Beispiel der Tempelanlage von Angkor Wat/Kambodscha
Denkmäler3.de - Industriearchäologie Przybilla HJ (ed) ISBN 978-3-8322-8301-8
- [6] AAVV 2015 Z+F IMAGER® 5010X User Manual v2.13 *Zoller + Fröhlich GmbH*
- [7] AAVV 2015 The X marks the spot. Z+F IMAGER® 5010X Data sheet *Zoller + Fröhlich GmbH*
- [8] AAVV 2015 Z+F LaserControl® Scout Manual v1.0 *Zoller + Fröhlich GmbH*
- [9] AAVV 2015 Z+F LaserControl® Manual v8.7 *Zoller + Fröhlich GmbH*